

Project	GUTTA
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Work Package title	Communication activities
Deliverable number	2.2.3
Deliverable title	At least four among video spots or clips in various languages
Deliverable Responsible Partner	CMCC
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1. Executive summary

The GUTTA project aims and results were disseminated through the realization of several videos (11), the majority of them (9) published on the CMCC YouTube Channel and organized in [a playlist](#)¹. The two remaining videos were live streamed and published on the [Adsp-MAM’s Facebook page](#)².

More in detail, the LP coordinated the activities for the realization of the final video of the project, being involved in the design and realization of the script and storyboard of the videos; in the realization of the texts, in English and in Italian, to be used by the speakers of the videos. Moreover, LP supported the video-maker in the iconographic research and in the editing of the videos. The text for the subtitles of the English version – subtitled in Croatian of the video was translated by MPPI, GUTTA project partner. The University of Zadar and CSA mare nostrum contributed to the realization of the GUTTA final videos by providing footages and photos.

The videos are all published in the GUTTA webpage on the Interreg Italy Croatia website (see the “VIDEO” section: <https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/gutta>)

Moreover, the videos had been extensively disseminated through GUTTA and PPs’ communication channels: institutional websites (news, press releases, event pages, etc), newsletters, mailing lists and social accounts.

¹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d16Xefoae-0&list=PLqj_l70M-izDbphwcbe48JoJqi6dsJp-8

² <https://www.facebook.com/Autorit%C3%A0-di-Sistema-Portuale-del-Mare-Adriatico-Meridionale-1808017536185486/>

2. Published resources

More in the detail, the project realized the following videos and playlist:

- 1) **The GUTTA playlist**, published on the CMCC YouTube Channel, available at the following url: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d16Xefoae-0&list=PLqj_l70M-izDbphwcbe48JoJqi6dsJp-8
- 2) the [GUTTA project final video](#), illustrating its main outcomes, both in English, in Italian, and in English – subtitled in Croatian;
- 3) the video-tutorial of the [GUTTA-VISIR](#) operational service for least-CO₂ ferry routes in the Adriatic and Northern Ionian Sea;
- 4) the video registration of [GUTTA final workshop in Lecce, Italy](#), a hybrid event held on May 4, 2022, in Lecce, Italy
- 5) the [video message of Maja Markovčić Kostelac, EMSA Director](#), on the occasion of GUTTA final workshop in Lecce, Italy;
- 6) the video registration of the online event “[You better watch out: learning how to prevent, tame and mitigate a pandemic \(COVID-19\)](#)” CMCC webinar organized in the framework of the GUTTA project and held on February 9, 2021;
- 7) the video registration of the online event “[Improving the sustainability of maritime transport in the Adriatic Sea](#)”, jointly organized by Interreg GUTTA, METRO and E-CHAIN projects and held on October 19, 2021;
- 8) The live streaming of the dissemination event “[The cooperation among the ports of the lower Adriatic and the upper Ionian: from the Programme Interreg 2014/2020 to 2021/2027](#)” held at the Cruise Terminal of the port of Bari on June 21, 2022;
- 9) The video reportage of the dissemination event “[The cooperation among the ports of the lower Adriatic and the upper Ionian: from the Programme Interreg 2014/2020 to 2021/2027](#)” held at the Cruise Terminal of the port of Bari on June 21, 2022;
- 10) the video illustrating the main results of a study realized in the framework of the project and investigating the carbon intensity of ferries ([more information here](#)).

Figure 1 Screenshot of GUTTA playlist published on the CMCC YouTube Channel.

2.1 Final video of the project

The screenshots in Figure 2-3-4 document the three final videos realized to illustrate the main results of the GUTTA project.

The English version is found at the URL: <https://youtu.be/JyEhrcsK19A>

The Italian version is found at the URL: <https://youtu.be/fO9lwWGa8qY>

The English version – subtitled in Croatian is found at the URL: <https://youtu.be/d16Xefoae-0>

Figure 2-3: Screenshots of the English and Italian versions of the GUTTA final video.

Title: GUTTA: research and innovation for an operational web tool for ship route optimization

Date of publication: 1 April 2022

Time: 3:07

Visualizations: 466

Title: GUTTA: ricerca e innovazione per l’ottimizzazione delle rotte

Date of publication: 30 May 2022

Time: 3:07

Visualizations: 65

Title: GUTTA: research and innovation for an operational web tool for ship route optimization - subtitled

Date of publication: 30 June 2022

Time: 3:07

Visualizations: 61

Figure 4: Screenshot of the English version – subtitled in Croatian of the GUTTA project final video.

2.2 GUTTA-VISIR video tutorial

The screenshot in Figure 5 document the video realized to illustrate the decision support tool GUTTA-VISIR, one of main result of the project.

The video is found at the URL: https://youtu.be/-qORsU-Jh_8

Title: Towards a more sustainable maritime transport in the Adriatic: the eco-routes of GUTTA-VISIR

Date of publication: 12 January 2022

Time: 1:34

Visualizations: 462

Figure 5: Screenshot of the video-tutorial of the GUTTA-VISIR operational service for least-CO₂ ferry routes in the Adriatic and Northern Ionian Sea (<https://www.gutta-visir.eu/>).

2.3 The videos realized during the events organized by GUTTA PPs

The live streaming of GUTTA project workshop "[Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation](#)", a hybrid event held on May 4, 2022, at CMCC premises in Lecce, Italy, is available at the following url: <https://youtu.be/7HLukdi5-bw>

The video message of Maja Markovčić Kostelac, EMSA Director, is available at the following url: <https://youtu.be/7AcBzAonZoU>

Title: Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation

Date of publication: 17 May 2022

Time: 5:58:28

Visualizations: 113 (180 during the live streaming of the event – here the link to this version of the video, before editing it: <https://youtu.be/f7A74MZTJTc>)

Title: GUTTA final workshop - Maja Markovčić Kostelac, EMSA Director

Date of publication: 30 May 2022

Time: 6:41

Visualizations: 46

Figure 6-7: Screenshots of the video registration of GUTTA final workshop "Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation", a hybrid event (in-person and online) held on May 4, 2022, in Lecce, Italy, and screenshot of the video message of Maja Markovčić Kostelac, EMSA Director, on the occasion of the GUTTA final workshop.

The video registration of the online event ["Improving the sustainability of maritime transport in the Adriatic Sea"](https://youtu.be/EfH8Y4nNiBw) is available at the following link: <https://youtu.be/EfH8Y4nNiBw>

Title: Improving the sustainability of the maritime transport

Date of publication: 20 October 2021

Time: 2:39:57

Visualizations: 109

Figure 8: Screenshot of the video registration of the online event "Improving the sustainability of maritime transport in the Adriatic Sea" jointly organized by GUTTA, METRO and E-CHAIN projects on October 19, 2021.

The video registration of the online event [“You better watch out: learning how to prevent, tame and mitigate a pandemic \(COVID-19\)”](https://youtu.be/rwRueoUchs4) is available at the following link: <https://youtu.be/rwRueoUchs4>

Title: You better watch out: learning how to prevent, tame and mitigate a pandemic (COVID-19)

Date of publication: 9 February 2021

Time: 49:00

Visualizations: 1208 visualizations

Figure 9: Screenshot of the video registration of the webinar “You better watch out: learning how to prevent, tame and mitigate a pandemic (COVID-19)” held online on February 9, 2021.

During the dissemination event [“The cooperation among the ports of the lower Adriatic and the upper Ionian: from the Programme Interreg 2014/2020 to 2021/2027”](#), a hybrid event organized by Adsp-MAM, GUTTA project partner, and held at the Cruise Terminal of the port of Bari on June 21, 2022, [a video reportage](#) was realized and the event was [live streamed on Facebook](#)

The video of the live streaming is available at the following url:

<https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=851151849177384>

Title: “The cooperation among the ports of the lower Adriatic and the upper Ionian...”

Visualizations: 355

Figure 10: Screenshot of the live streaming of the dissemination event “The cooperation among the ports of the lower Adriatic and the upper Ionian: from the Programme Interreg 2014/2020 to 2021/2027” held at the Cruise Terminal of the port of Bari on June 21, 2022.

The video reportage of the event is available at the following url:

<https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=1098129187787166>

Title: “#portodibari: è stata un'ottima occasione di confronto e di dialogo il convegno organizzato nei giorni scorsi da #adspmam con i progetti...”

Visualizations: 110

Figure 11: Screenshot of the video reportage of the dissemination event “The cooperation among the ports of the lower Adriatic and the upper Ionian: from the Programme Interreg 2014/2020 to 2021/2027” held at the Cruise Terminal of the port of Bari on June 21, 2022.

2.4 The video “Investigating the carbon intensity of ferries”

In June 2019, information about CO₂ emissions from ships in the European Economic Area were published for the first time ever. This information was vessel-distinctive and open-access, enabling further investigations by citizens and scientists. In the frame of GUTTA project, researchers at CMCC explored these data and augmented them with additional vessel-related information. They focused on ferries, a category of over-proportionally emitting ships. Results reveal the geographical distribution of monitoring methods used and CO₂ emissions, as well as the complexity of the relationship between carbon intensity and other vessel parameters.

This video realized by the CMCC illustrates the main results of this study realized in the framework of the project and investigating the carbon intensity of ferries ([more information here](#)).

The video is available at the following url: <https://youtu.be/Nez456wsfvc>

Title: Investigating the carbon intensity of ferries

Date of publication: 18 December 2020

Time: 3:19

Visualizations: 141

Figure 12: Screenshot of the video realized to illustrate the results of the study realized by the CMCC Foundation.